

STUDIES ON SULPHONAMIDES AND ANALOGOUS COMPOUNDS. PART III

By U. P. BASU

Certain derivatives of sulpha drugs, obtained by substituting the N⁴-hydrogen atom of the sulphanilamide compounds, have been prepared and described.

It is now generally accepted that sulphonamide drugs act by interfering with the essential metabolites of the pathogenic organisms and that the mechanism of their action in general is more or less the same. The difference that is noticed in their activity against a given strain of bacteria, is explained by their different degree of adsorption to the bacteria, by differences in their blood concentration, excretion and toxicity, and partly by some unspecific activity introduced by the substituent at N¹-atom (cf. Julius and Salomen, *Ant. v. Leeuwenhoek*, 1941, 7, 77). The basic behaviour of all sulphonamides is remarkably alike, all are inhibited by *p*-aminobenzoic acid, and any substitution in the amino group (N⁴-atom) of the sulphonamides alters the chemotherapeutic activity to a considerable extent. The researches of Klotz (*Science*, 1943, 98, 60) and Davis and Wood (*Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1942, 51, 283) tend to establish again that the activity of any sulphonamide derivative would depend much on its dissociation constant (cf. Bell and Roblin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2905) and the tendency towards complex formation with enzyme protein. It is for this that the anion or the *p*-"NH₂" group of a sulphonamide drug plays a greater rôle in determining its *in vivo* activity. Accordingly, continuous effort is being made to discover a derivative that might allow the active component to be present at the site of infection. The observations of Poth and Ross (*J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1944, 29, 785) as well as that of Bhatnagar *et al.* (*Brit. Med. J.*, 1948, i, 719) point to the same conclusion. In this laboratory work is being followed in this direction (cf. Sikdar and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 22, 343) to produce compounds that might be effective against intestinal infections.

The 4-hydroxymethylamino derivatives that have been prepared from sulphanilylbenzamide, sulphacetamide, sulphadiazine sulphamerazine and sulphamethazine by reacting with formalin or hexamine have been described in the body of this paper. Their *in vitro* activity against both the strains (*Inaba* and *Ogawa*) of *V. cholerae*, *Shigella* and *Salmonella* organisms are being studied and would be reported elsewhere. The 4-hydroxymethylaminobenzene sulphonbenzamide and the corresponding derivative of sulphadiazine have been found to be the most active. The latter is soluble in dilute acid but the former is insoluble. The sulphanilyl benzamide derivative being further soluble in dilute alkali may be readily administered through parenteral route and as such may be useful in cases of emergency. While the work was in progress a private information on the efficacy of phthalyl sulphacetamide led us to the synthesis of this compound and to compare its characteristics with phthalyl sulphanilylbenzamide previously studied (Sikdar and Basu, *loc. cit.*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Reaction with Formalin.—The sulphonamide compound was dissolved in dilute alcohol and the clear solution was filtered off. While hot it was mixed with an alcoholic solution of formalin containing about 1.25 molar amount of formaldehyde. In cases of sulphanilylbenzamide and sulphacetamide crystals soon separated out almost in theoretical yield and were collected after cooling the reaction mixture at 5°. The *p*-hydroxymethylaminobenzene sulphonbenzamide (sulphanilyl benzamide derivative) crystallises out from alcohol (95%) or better from acetone in crops of fine crystals, m.p. 160°; whereas the corresponding derivative from sulphacetamide separated from water in needles, m. p. 222° (decomp.) The reaction mixtures in cases of sulphadiazine, sulphamerazine and sulphamezathine were crystallised from alcohol (95%) in minute crystalline forms melting at 254°, 240° and 242° respectively and depressing the melting points of the parent compounds when mixed in equal proportions.

Reaction with Hexamine.—The identical compounds were obtained by refluxing the sulphonamide derivative with molecular proportion of hexamine in dilute alcoholic solution for a period of half an hour to one hour. During heating ammonia vapour was found to escape and the reaction mixture had to be neutralised to obtain the maximum yield of the condensation product. The products obtained by this process showed no depression in melting point when admixed with equal proportions of the products obtained by the formalin reaction.

General Characteristics of the Compounds.—All the compounds obtained as above are soluble in dilute alkali, and readily reduces a silver nitrate solution to metallic silver on warming. They give no diazo reaction but dissolve in concentrated acids not precipitating on dilution with water. The 4-hydroxymethylaminobenzene sulphonbenzamide and the corresponding acetamide are insoluble in dilute acid; whereas the methylal derivatives from sulphadiazine, sulphamerazine and sulphamezathine are soluble in dilute acids. The compounds are not appreciably altered when heated with 0.36% hydrochloric acid at 40° for about 3 hours; but they undergo hydrolysis to the parent

TABLE I

Compound : Structure—HO.CH₂NH₂.C₆H₄.SO₂.NH.R

R =	Formula	Melting point.	Nitrogen	
			Calc.	Found.
Benzoyl ...	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S	160°	9.15%	8.95%
Acetyl ...	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ S	222°	11.47	11.80
Pyrimidyl ...	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₄ S	254°	20.0	19.1
4-Methyl ..	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	240°	19.04	18.4
4 :6-Dimethyl ..	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	232°	18.18	18.0
Hydrogen ...	C ₇ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	112°	13.86	14.0

compound with liberation of formaldehyde when slowly heated with dilute (5%) caustic soda solution. Presence of free *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide compound is detectable on acidification of the reacted solution and subsequent diazotisation. None of the products decolorise biomine solution, nor interact with a solution of sodium bisulphite. The other properties are shown in the table above.

Phthalylsulphacetamide.—Freshly sublimed phthalic anhydride (2.1 g.) was added slowly to a hot absolute alcoholic solution of sulphacetamide (3.6 g.), and the whole was refluxed for more than 2 hours. The clear solution was filtered, evaporated and acidified with hydrochloric acid. A solid separated out; this was filtered off and dissolved in sodium carbonate solution. A trace remained undissolved; this was filtered off and the mother-liquor was again acidified to Congo red when the phthalyl derivative separated out. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 196°. (Found: N, 7.70. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6N_2S$ requires N, 7.73 per cent).

BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
CALCUTTA.

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